

When 3 to 4 mm long anther calluses were subcultured in auxin-free regeneration medium, plantlets formed within 15 to 20 days, and were albino or normal. Of the calluses plated from ASD8/Amaravathi, 16% produced green plants, and ASD8/Bagavathi formed 22% green plants. ASD8/Vaigai produced only albinos and ASD8/Zhinjan regenerated only roots (Table 2). □

Table 2. Regeneration of plants from anther calluses of Tamil Nadu Agricultural University rices, 1980.

cross	Anther calluses subcultured (no.)	Green plantlets (%)	Albinos (%)	Roots alone (%)	No differentiation (%)
ASD8/Vaigai (F ₁)	40	—	25	48	27
ASD8/Amaravathi (F ₁)	72	16	—	64	20
ASD8/Bagavathi (F ₂)	90	22	—	49	29
ASD8/Zhinjan (F ₁)	24	—	—	68	32

Pest management and control DISEASES

Effect of slow-release nitrogen fertilizers on rice brown spot disease

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Brown spot (BS) *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan is becoming a serious disease of high yielding rice varieties in Tamil Nadu. Heavy nitrogen fertilizer application increases BS incidence.

A field trial in kuruvai (Jul-Oct) with the short-duration (105–110 day) variety TKM9 measured the effect of slow-release nitrogen fertilizer on BS incidence. Commercial urea, sulfur-coated urea, and urea supergranule (1-g size) were applied at 29, 58, 87, and 110 kg N/ha in a randomized

Effect of different forms of urea on BS incidence in rice.

Treatment	Disease intensity ^a at nitrogen levels				
	0	29 kg N/ha	58 kg N/ha	87 kg N/ha	110 kg N/ha
Commercial urea	—	5.1	5.0	4.6	5.0
Sulfur-coated urea	—	4.7	2.4	2.9	1.9
Urea supergranule	—	4.0	4.3	2.7	3.3
No nitrogen	5.6	—	—	—	—

^aBased on 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. Least significant difference at 5% level = 1.4.

block design with 3 replications. Urea was applied in two equal split doses: at transplanting and panicle initiation. Sulfur-coated urea was incorporated at transplanting. Urea supergranule was spot applied, one granule for every 4 hills, 15 days after transplanting. Phosphorus and potassium were applied at 50 kg/ha to all plots. Disease incidence was assessed at growth stage 9, using the Standard

Evaluation System for Rice.

No application and heavy application of urea caused heavy BS incidence. Application of sulfur-coated urea or urea supergranule appreciably reduced disease incidence (see table). These two fertilizers can be applied at levels from 87 to 110 kg N/ha with good reduction in disease incidence. Sulfur-coated urea performed better than urea supergranule. □

Response of two rice varieties to *Rhynchosporium oryzae* infection.

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Earlier qualitative observations have indicated that in Sierra Leone narrow-leaf rice varieties were less affected by rice leaf scald fungus *Rhynchosporium oryzae* Hashioka & Yokogi than broadleaf varieties. During 1979 and 1980 wet seasons (May-Oct), field experiments compared the response of ROK 16 (broad-leaf) and PN623-3 (narrow-leaf) to *R. oryzae* infection either with or without benomyl fungicide. Experiments were at

Table 1. Response of 2 rice varieties to *Rhynchosporium oryzae* infection in Sierra Leone.^a

Experimental site	Treatment	Leaf area infected (%)	
		ROK16	PN623-3
<i>1979</i>			
Sendugu-NP	Benomyl	0.9	0.8
	Untreated	3.4*	2.8*
Makassa-NP	Benomyl	2.2	2.5
	Untreated	5.2*	4.2*
<i>1980</i>			
Masorie-NP	Benomyl	0.5	1.5
	Untreated	5.9	7.0
Sendugu-NP	Benomyl	0.4	0.3
	Untreated	1.6	1.3
Kenema-EP	Benomyl	0.1	0.1
	Untreated	0.2	0.3

^aValues are means from the 4 top leaves in 1979 and from the 3 top leaves in 1980. NP = Northern Province, within 8 km from RRS; EP = Eastern Province, 360 km from RRS. ROK16 and PN623-3 have broad-droopy and narrow-erect leaves, respectively. For 1979, *denotes significant difference between benomyl-treated and untreated values; differences between varieties are not significant, $P = 0.05$. For 1980, LSD ($P = 0.05$) are 1.2 (Masorie), 0.7 (Sendugu), 0.1 (Kenema). Untreated plants were artificially inoculated at Masorie.

four RRS upland experimental sites (Table 1).

In 1979 the experiments were conducted separately for each variety in randomized, treated and untreated paired plots replicated six times. Seeds were drilled at 80 kg/ha with 20 cm between rows. In 1980 the experiments were carried out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Four or five seeds were sown in hills spaced 20 × 15 cm. Plot size was 6 × 2 m, and treated plots received 4 sprayings of benomyl between tillering and dough stages at 0.33 kg ai/ha per spray. About 20 randomly chosen fertile tillers per plot were assessed for infection.

Percentages of the visible area of the leaf lamina infected, from the flag leaf and from three (1979) and two (1980) successive leaves for each tiller selected were averaged for each plot at dough stage in 1979, and at boot and dough stages in 1980. Infection rates between boot and dough stages were calculated for the 1980 experiments.

The varieties did not significantly differ in leaf area infected (Table 1). This

Table 2. *Rhynchosporium oryzae* infection rates between boot and dough stages in 2 rice varieties in 1980 in Sierra Leone^a

Experimental site	Treatment	Infection rate ^b	
		ROK16	PN623-3
Masorie-NP	Benomyl	0.044	0.046
	Untreated	0.043	0.057
Sendugu-NP	Benomyl	0.016	0.003
	Untreated	0.041	0.026
Kenema-EP	Benomyl	0.012	0.029
	Untreated	0.029	0.039

^aNP = Northern Province, within 8 km from RRS; EP = Eastern Province, 360 km from RRS. ROK16 and PN623-3 have broad-droopy and narrow-erect leaves, respectively. LSD ($P = 0.05$) are 0.043 (Masorie), 0.043 (Sendugu), 0.030 (Kenema). Untreated plants were artificially inoculated at Masorie. ^bAfter Van der Plank.

observation was also true for the Masorie experiment in 1980 where plots which did not receive benomyl were artificially inoculated with *R. oryzae* conidia at maximum tillering stage. Symptoms from natural inoculum were rarely apparent before maximum tillering. Average leaf area infected in untreated plots was relatively low — between 0.2 and 5.9% for ROK16 and 0.3 and 7% for PN623-3.

Average infection was lowest in the flag leaves and increased progressively on the leaves below. The differences in infec-

tion rates were not significant ($P = 0.05$) (Table 2). Benomyl significantly reduced infection and, except for one instance, slowed the infection rate. In plots where enough disease developed to cause loss, average losses for both years were 15.3% for ROK16 and 12.6% for PN623-3. Correlation coefficients (r) between percent leaf area infected and yield for plots were significant ($P = 0.05$) only when r was calculated separately for each variety at each site for a given year. □

Rice tungro virus complex in tungro-resistant IR varieties

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Tungro disease is associated with a virus complex composed of small bacilliform and isometric virus particles recently described as rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). Diseased plants exhibited severe symptoms when infected with both particles; mild symptoms with RTBV alone; and are almost symptomless with RTSV alone.

The presence of the RTV complex on IR36, IR42, IR50, IR54, and IR56, bred as tungro-resistant varieties, was determined by the latex agglutination test using antisera to RTBV and RTSV, and the virus recovery test using the vector insect *Nephotettix virescens*. Tungro-infected plants were obtained by inoculating 6-day-old seedlings with 1 insect per seedling in test tubes for 24 hours.

The latex agglutination test involved

A light micrograph shows clumping of latex particles indicating the presence of virus (right). No clumping (left) indicates absence of virus.

mixing equal volumes of a very small amount of plant sap and a suspension of latex particles (Difco Bacto Latex 0.81) treated with an antiserum. The mixture was then agitated vigorously for 5–10

min. The presence of the virus in the plant sap was indicated by the clumping or agglutination of the latex particles as observed under the light microscope (see figure).